

Active Thermal Cycling of Discrete Power Semiconductors for Applications with strong ΔT -Profiles

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel test system, which is optimized to simulate temperature mission profiles of various applications, which exhibit large temperature changes. The aim is to treat the investigated power semiconductor as a “black box” without the need for a lifetime model. A microcontroller controls the self-heating of the device under test to generate the necessary power losses. Simultaneously the microcontroller acquires measurement data of the device under test (DUT) based on a pre-defined test plan. To simulate also negative ambient temperatures the DUT is mounted on a cooling system. The test system has a high flexibility within a wide temperature range and can be used to simulate various application conditions, especially for applications with a large temperature swing. A mission profile focusing on the application of power semiconductors within solar inverters is used as a reference. Based on such a mission profile, heating current, gate voltage and chiller temperature are adjusted automatically to drive the system to all temperature conditions the DUT is expected to be exposed to during its lifetime in its target application.

1 Introduction

Power semiconductor packages continuously improve in order to achieve a higher reliability, better performance and robustness. This leads to more complex interconnections within the package. In order to be able to predict lifetime and performance, more sophisticated models in combination with common power cycling tests are of paramount importance [1–5]. Other approaches perform virtual junction temperature cycles and monitor electrical parameters determined as aging precursors in combination with complex algorithms to estimate the lifetime [6]. Additionally, next to common applications, where the device undergoes nearly no high amount of temperature cycles, there are also applications with strong temperature change profiles. In order to predict the lifetime of such thermomechanically demanding applications, the lifetime model needs to be even more complex [7].

Therefore, it is of advantage to have an active thermal cycling test, which is able to perform real temperature mission profiles tailored to the target application. This approach forgoes the need to apply widely used degradation models with their inherent uncertainties with respect to the used acceleration factors. The main focus of the here presented test is the degradation inside the package due to application-oriented thermal changes.

With this application-oriented power cycling test, a model is not required as long as the mission profile is defined well enough to cover all ΔT s that are expected to happen over the lifetime. Since there are applications with extreme temperature levels, the test should be able to perform temperature cycles between -40°C and 150°C . The maximum temperature of the power semiconductor for a particular

test-run is determined by the device specifications. As this temperature range is not common for electronic components, the control and measurement circuits should not undergo these extreme temperature changes. This would impose either extreme requirements or decrease the accuracy and lifetime of the test system.

2 Approach

As a first step, the basic principle of the test is defined and shown in Figure 1. A temperature control unit regulates the temperature of a heat sink, which is set to a lower temperature than the required minimum temperature of the temperature cycle. The main advantage of using liquid cooling instead a climate chamber is, that only the parts connected to the heatsink are affected by the cooling.

Figure 1 Basic working principle of the test

Also a higher cooling power can be achieved using liquid cooling, which enables faster cool-down times of the device under test. To generate the power loss in the component, a power supply unit provides a certain current to achieve enough conduction losses, similar to traditional

power cycling. The measured temperature is the average case temperature of the device recorded using an infrared sensor. This sensor is connected to a local control unit based on a microcontroller, which is also responsible for controlling the component. Many lifetime test systems are designed with the attempt to determine the virtual junction temperature of the DUT during the stress.

However, for the defined application relevant test cycles a thermal model would be needed. Such an approach needs a complex thermal model and also an online update or recalibration of the thermal model as the DUT could degrade over time [8, 9]. Therefore, this test system focuses on the control of the case temperature. Chiller, power supply unit and the local control unit are connected to a host computer. This host is the central control unit of the entire test system. The temperature change test profile can be adapted easily via the host software. Such flexibility makes it possible to easily adapt the system to various mission profiles.

This testplan is executed using an existing software environment [10]. For the here described test system, the coolant temperature, the drain current I_D and the gate voltage V_{GS} of the DUT can be configured. With a variable coolant temperature, the time for cooling down the DUT can be specified. For the heating, I_D and V_{GS} can be varied in order to achieve different temperature changes.

However, for a given I_D and DUT, there is a certain range for V_{GS} where a stable operation of the DUT is possible. The lower limit for V_{GS} is determined by the thermal stable point. Below this point thermal runaway of the DUT would become a severe issue [11, 12]. The upper limit for V_{GS} is given by the device's maximum rating. Furthermore, the test system records measurement data such as the DUT's case temperature, its Drain-Source and Gate-Source voltages for later analysis.

2.1 Controller strategy

In Figure 2 a more detailed block diagram shows how the controller works. As an input, the minimum and maximum or a sequence of temperature points are needed. For the heating of the DUT the on-time and I_D are fixed to a certain value.

Figure 2 Detailed block diagram of the test system including relevant parameters to control the device

The controller turns off the DUT either after the fixed on-time or if a maximum temperature is exceeded to protect the device. By controlling the DUT's V_{GS} a certain temperature profile can be fine-tuned. The time to cool down the device can only be varied by changing the coolant temperature of the chiller.

A higher coolant temperature increases the time needed to cool down the device and vice versa. The upper limit for the coolant temperature is determined by the thermal resistance between the coolant and the DUT. The lower the coolant temperature, the faster the cool down of the device. But setting the coolant temperature too low means also, that more power needs to be dissipated within the DUT to reach the desired maximum temperature. The logic part of the test plan defines the reference input of the controller and is also able to disable it.

This is needed during cooling because the cooling of the device cannot be influenced by the V_{GS} controller. After each heating pulse, the controller compares the measured case temperature to the reference and adapts the gate voltage for the next cycle. When the device is not reaching the desired temperature, the V_{GS} is decreased as a first measure. If V_{GS} reaches the lower limit of the specified V_{GS} range and the target temperature can still not be reached, I_D is increased via the current of the PSU. To overcome this time-consuming procedure, the device is turned on and a proper combination of V_{GS} and I_D is determined before the test cycles start.

2.2 Test setup

The device under test is soldered onto a carrier board as shown in Figure 3. As most of the heat from the chip is transferred through the leadframe of the package, a large number of vias are placed near to the leadframe. This forms a path for the heat to flow to the bottom of the PCB.

Figure 3 Substrate with soldered DUT surrounded by via-matrix for better thermal connection

On the bottom side of the PCB a thermal interface material (TIM) is added for electrical insulation. To make a generalization possible in terms of thermal conditions, a thermal resistance test is performed after assembly which detects poorly soldered DUTs.

A mechanical construction, shown in Figure 4, is used to apply a reproducible force to the substrate. This enables a good thermal connection of the substrate to the heatsink. In parallel, the electrical connection is done and also the infrared sensor is positioned above the DUT by the mechanical construction. Electrical connections are available from the top via the pads on the outer edge of the PCB.

The main benefit of this construction is, that the substrate with the DUT can be easily and quickly replaced and used for detailed measurements on other characterization equip-

ment. This is very important when several DUTs need to be tested. For other packages a separate substrate is needed. The maximum package size is defined by the pads for the electrical connection. The location of these pads must be the same in order to fit into the mechanical construction. The microcontroller with its peripherals is located on a separate PCB.

Figure 4 (a) Virtual prototype and (b) real implementation of the mechanical construction used for the electrical and thermal interconnection of the DUT PCBs.

3 Mission Profile Definition

To demonstrate the capabilities of the system a mission profile of a solar application is used. Discrete power semiconductors inside solar inverters undergo numerous different temperatures over their lifetime [13, 14]. The lowest temperature is reached when there is no solar radiation and the power semiconductor consequently reaches the ambient temperature.

Depending on the location and season the ambient temperature in the converter box can start at e.g. $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and reach up to $70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. In addition, there is the self-heating of the main power MOSFET. As a result components within the converter box can easily heat up to the maximum rated temperature. The rate at which this happens depends on the strength of the solar radiation [15], the heat dissipation of the power devices and the climate conditions in the converter housing.

To provide a useful testable temperature profile, that mimics the typical temperature changes over lifetime, the superposition of the following conditions need to be considered:

1. Seasonal ambient temperature change throughout a year, e.g. $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
2. Daily temperature variations $\pm 10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ on top of 1.
3. Electrical self-heating of the power MOSFET in addition to 1. and 2.
4. Increased temperature due to closed housing conditions in the converter box.

In total daily temperature variations that range from $-30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during winter times and $45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ during summer times may occur. The overall temperature

includes also the internal heating of the electronics in operating mode. If this operating phase is interrupted, e.g. by clouds, the self-heating is strongly reduced and a sudden temperature drop occurs. Also this temperature change has to be taken into account. Therefore, our temperature profiles reflect also such events by simulating a switch-off event once a day under full-load conditions.

If a binning of the temperature profile is used, e.g. in $15\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ -steps, the temperature change profile simplifies to the structure that is displayed in Figure 5. Each “M” represents a typical daily profile in binned mode, including a switch-off event at full-load conditions.

These “M”-shapes have to be repeated at different starting temperatures to mimic all temperature changes of a year. Solar applications have a long lifetime expectation, typically 25 years. So the above derived temperature profile needs to be extended to cover a whole year and then repeated 25 times.

Figure 5 Test cycles for a solar inverter application simulating one year of a solar application profile.

This results in 36500 temperature changes, where the starting temperature and ΔT changes according to the profile. Due to the high amount of temperature changes the heating and cooling times have to be optimized. There has to be a trade-off between the temperature change time and the hold time. It has to be ensured that after a change event the entire package is at the target temperature, before the next change starts.

The here presented concept focuses only on the degradation caused by transient temperature events. One of the intentions is to test the robustness of a particular design given the numerous different coefficients of thermal expansion within a DUT. Therefore, long hold times at steady temperature can be avoided to save test time.

Since the time it takes to reach a sufficient thermal equilibrium depends on the DUT and the aforementioned boundary conditions the hold time needs to be adjusted accordingly.

4 Results

To verify the functionality of the system and the implemented controller the *M6* cycle defined in Figure 5 is used. For each cycle initial values for V_{GS} and I_D need to be defined. This needs to be done once for each new DUT type as parameters like transfer characteristic, channel resistance and thermal resistance change.

As each DUT substrate has a different thermal resistance as well as slightly other electrical characteristics, the controller needs to adjust this small deviation at the start-up of the test. Such a start-up can be seen in Figure 6, where the maximum device temperature of each pulse, which is used as a controller input, and V_{GS} of the DUT are shown over two hundred *M6* cycles.

Figure 6 Performance of the controller over two hundred *M6* cycles.

It can be seen that in this case the initial gate voltage is too high, which results in a device temperature above the reference. The adjustment of the gate voltage takes only 4 “*M*” cycles in the shown case. After this start-up procedure the controller only needs to change V_{GS} only slightly, which is mainly caused by the tolerance of the infrared sensor.

4.1 Impact of the coolant temperature

To show the impact of the chiller, the *M6* cycles are performed with three different coolant temperatures. This comparison is shown in Figure 7 for 35 °C, 40 °C and 45 °C. The depicted cycles have been recorded after the start-up phase of the controller, i.e. any of the controller’s aforementioned adjustments have already occurred.

The cool-down time is decreasing with increasing coolant temperature and therefore variable. In order to meet the requirements of the defined mission profile, a 45° coolant temperature is preferred as a slow cooling is desirable in this case.

As mentioned in Section 2.1, in contrast to the cool-down time, the heating of the device is limited to a certain specified on-time. The selected on-time for the curves in Figure 7 has been chosen such that the chip within the DUT’s

package will have reached a close to quasi thermal equilibrium. Further increasing the on-time would result only in a few more degrees on the DUT’s case where the temperature is measured. This is mainly related to the high time constant of the heatsink within the overall thermal network caused by it’s big thermal mass in comparison to the DUT.

Figure 7 Impact of coolant temperature on cooling time for *M6* test cycles.

The fast drop of temperature in the middle of the cycle is of interest as it should emulate a small cloud passing event. The heating to the maximum and the cooling to the lowest reference temperature of each cycle should be slower. Also nearly steady-state should be reached before turning off or on the device.

4.2 Test cycles verification

In order to verify the functionality of the test system, all test cycles for selected solar mission profile are performed. The measured device temperature for each “*M*” is shown in Figure 8.

Each of the six “*M*” cycles take less than thirty seconds, which is important for the overall test time. In general the hold time is a result of the specified on time. For the test cycles shown, the on time is selected so that thermal equilibrium is almost reached. All cycles have the same on time and therefore similar heating curves.

The main difference is the cooling time, which is caused by different coolant temperatures. Choosing the right coolant temperature is a challenge if the cooling time should match the heating time. This is mainly influenced by the losses inside the thermal stack-up and the environmental conditions.

For all performed measurements, the ambient temperature was 22°. To reach negative DUT temperatures, the coolant must be much colder than the target temperature. The closer the lowest target temperature is to the ambient temperature, the smaller the difference to the coolant temperature must be.

Also the current supplied by the PSU needs to be higher,

Figure 8 Verification and comparison of measured device temperature for all defined “M” test cycles.

the colder the coolant temperature is. In Table 1 the current through the device and the selected coolant temperature are listed for the cycles shown in Figure 8. The results have shown that the system is able to perform all defined test cycles. Of course, selecting the proper current, coolant temperature and initial gate voltage is crucial and must be defined before a test starts.

Table 1 Coolant temperature and device current for the “M” cycle validation measurements.

	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
$T_{coolant}$ in °C	-50	-25	-5	10	28	45
I_{DUT} in A	52,5	49	47	44,5	43	41

5 Conclusion and Outlook

A novel approach for active thermal cycling with a high flexibility to simulate different mission profiles and ΔT -requirements is presented in this paper. This enables an improved experimental assessment of device robustness without the usage of complex acceleration models. A controller concept is introduced and verified through a case study of typical temperature profiles from solar inverter applications.

As a next step the herein proposed method will be applied to various DUTs to emulate their lifetime and investigate the degradation caused by the test. In addition, the impact of various heating and cooling slopes will be investigated to determine which level of test acceleration is possible. The herein proposed method assumes that the degradation is caused only by the thermal mismatch of the different materials within the chip package. This means, that test results should ideally not depend on the heating and cooling transients themselves.

To prove this assumption, further tests are necessary to de-

termine how much the cycles can be accelerated without triggering an artificial degradation. Future work will also focus on an improvement of the test to perform mission profiles on multiple devices in parallel located on the same heatsink.

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